

QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF BARELY VISIBLE INDENTATION DAMAGE (BVID) IN CF/EP SANDWICH COMPOSITES USING GUIDED WAVE SIGNALS

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1 Introduction

A sandwich structure consists of two strong panels separated by a lightweight core such as honeycomb. The separation increases the moment of inertia with only a slight increase in weight, producing an efficient structure for resisting bending and buckling loads. Composite sandwich structures are applied to primary components in aerospace applications, therefore they are susceptible to incur impact damage which creates a major concern related to structural integrity [1-2].

Low velocity impacts are caused by various sources from bird strikes, dropping tools on parts during manufacturing and servicing or runway debris during takeoff. Such impacts could easily crush the core or create a dent on the surface of the skin [2-3]. The low velocity impact can produce widespread core damage which can significantly reduce the residual strength due to the deterioration in the mechanical properties of both the skins and the core [3]. Those types of impact usually produce hidden damage which is referred to as Barely Visible Indentation (or Impact) Damage (BVID). Structures with existing damage, in operation, may lead to the extension of the damage severity, eventually causing a catastrophic failure [1].

Great efforts have been made to describe the BVID phenomena and consequently develop methods to detect and assess the severity of BVID. Ruzek et al. [4] conducted a study to compare various methods to inspect composite sandwich structures after impact, including visual, C-scan and shearography. C-Scan may not be very suitable for BVID detection while

shearography can perform better, and as expected the visual method are not efficient when dealing with BVID for low energy impact. Takeda et al. [5] demonstrated the capability of fibre bragg grating (FBG) sensors to detect BVID in composite wing structures during integrity tests after impact. They identified the damage by monitoring the change in signals of FBG sensors due to the existence of damage. Other studies [6-7] were based on nonlinear elastic wave spectroscopy to identify BVID in CF/EP composites, as the severe damage usually influences one of dynamic characteristics of composites, such as the shift in resonance frequency or the presence of harmonics and sidebands on the spectrum of the dynamic signals.

Guided waves can propagate for relatively long distances, and they have high sensitivity to both surface and embedded structural damage such as delamination, de-bonding, holes, cracks/notches and corrosion in both composite and metallic components [8-13]. In this study, guided waves are used to identify BVID in CF/EP sandwich composites, which is quantitatively assessed using a damage index (DI) based on changes in transmitted guided wave signals.

2 Experimental

Composite sandwich panels were manufactured using CF/EP woven fabric prepreg [14], consisting of surface CF/EP laminates in a quasi-isotropic configuration [$\pm 45, 0/90$]_s with a nominal thickness of 0.88 mm, and a core of Nomex honeycomb (20.4 mm in thickness) [15]. The CF/EP laminate was initially cured in an autoclave following the required

procedures. The surface CF/EP laminates and the core were bonded together with FM 1515-3 film adhesive [16] using secondary bonding in the autoclave. Sandwich beams of 560 mm in length and 30 mm in width were cut from the sandwich panels, and the panels were trimmed to 560 mm by 560 mm in dimension. The properties of the sandwich CF/EP composite panels are summarized in Table 1.

For the panel, a sensor network was created consisting of sixteen circular PZTs with a distance of 100 mm between elements, enclosing a square area. PZT elements (P1 to P16) measuring 10 mm in diameter and 1 mm in thickness, were surface-mounted on each of the sandwich panels, using Loctite Superglue. While one PZT element acts as actuator in order to activate wave signals, the others function as sensors to capture the wave signals, and the role of actuator alternated until all the PZT elements had functioned as the actuator. As for the sensor network on the beam, three circular PZT

elements were surface-mounted on the beam specimens. PZT 1 served as the actuator while PZT 2 and PZT 3 served as sensors. PZT 2 was placed 350 mm apart from PZT 1, symmetrically about the centre of the beam, while PZT 3 was placed on the opposite surface of the beam and positioned underneath PZT 2. The panel and beam specimens were simply supported during the experiment.

Sinusoidal tonebursts (60V peak-to-peak) enclosed in a Hanning window were used as the input signal for the actuator. Activation and acquisition of wave signals were fulfilled using an active signal generation and data acquisition system developed on the VXI platform, consisting mainly of a signal generation unit (Agilent[®] E1441), signal amplifier (PiezoSys[®] EPA-104), signal conditioner (Agilent[®] E3242A) and signal digitizer (Agilent[®] E1437A). The wave signals were captured at a sampling rate of 5.12 MHz. The acquisition duration was set to insure that the activated wave modes were captured.

Table 1. Properties of CF/EP composite sandwich panels

(a) Plain woven fabric CF/EP composite laminate

E_{11}	E_{22}	G_{12}	G_{23}	G_{31}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	Density
55.8 GPa	55.8 GPa	3.65 GPa	3.65 GPa	3.65 GPa	0.06	0.05	0.38	1600 kg/m ³

(b) Nomexcore (HRH 10 1/8-4)

Cell Diameter	Core Thickness	Density
3.2 mm	20.4 mm	64 kg/m ³

3 Wave Signals for Damage Identification

In this study two methods were adopted to define the damage index (DI), based on a) the correlation between the reconstructed and the original wave signals after the TR (time-reversal) process, and (b) the magnitude of the wave signals captured from the intact plate compared to those captured after damage.

The principle of the TR process in a two-dimensional plate (Fig. 1) is described as the following. When a tone burst signal $V_A(\omega)$ at a central frequency ω is applied to transducer A (step

1), it activates a wave signal that propagates in the domain. The activated wave signal is captured by transducer B (step 2), defined by $V_B(\omega)$. When V_B is time-reversed, amplified and applied as a wave signal burst to transducer B, now acting as an actuator following the same procedure (step 3), the wave signal at transducer A is captured and time-reversed as $V'_A(\omega)$ (step 4). In principle, if there is no anomaly along the wave propagation path between transducers A and B, theoretically $V'_A(t)$ is similar to $V_A(t)$ in the time domain, and the shape of the constructed signal $V'_A(t)$ should be the same as the original input signal $V_A(t)$ after normalizing.

However, a defect in (or near) a wave path results in a dispersion in the wave's central frequency. In addition, the shape of the reconstructed wave signal $V'_A(t)$ after interaction with damage will differ from that of the original $V_A(t)$ after normalizing, depending on the degree of the wave form distortion. With the original wave signal $V_A(t)$ and the reconstructed wave signal $V'_A(t)$ after time-reversal in the time domain, a DI can be defined by the difference between the two [17], and the perception of damage can be obtained without requiring the other baseline signals for comparison [18].

The changes between the original wave signal V_A , $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ and the reconstructed one after time-reversal V'_A $\{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n\}$ of a sensing path can quantitatively be measured by the correlation coefficient, defined by [19]

$$\rho_{a,b}(t) = \frac{n \sum a_i b_i - \sum a_i \sum b_i}{\sqrt{[n \sum a_i^2 - (\sum a_i)^2][n \sum b_i^2 - (\sum b_i)^2]}} \quad (1)$$

Before the correlation, both V_A and V'_A are normalized to compensate for dispersion in wave energy. The value of $\rho_{a,b}(t)$ defines the degree of similarity between two signals, V_A and V'_A . When each signal is perfectly approximated by the other, $\rho_{a,b}(t) = 1$.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the time-reversal process: generation and acquisition of signals

Furthermore, the correlation coefficient approaches unity if the sensing path is very distant from the damage (when the captured signal is not affected by the damage), but it decreases the closer the sensing path is to the damage, reflecting the fact that the time reversibility of the captured wave signal deteriorates after it interacts with damage. The DI is defined as the similarity, $\rho_{a,b}(t)$, of the wave signals subtracted from a unity [19].

$$DI = 1 - \rho_{a,b}(t) \quad (2)$$

In this way, the higher the DI, the higher the possibility of the existence of damage or the closer the damage to the wave path, defined by the time reversibility of the input wave signal.

For the second method, the DI for the transmitted wave signals can simply be defined as.

$$DI = 1 - \frac{h}{h_0} \quad (3)$$

where h_0 is the baseline wave magnitude before the damage, whilst h is the wave magnitude after damage.

The monitoring area was meshed into uniform grids and the presence of damage at each grid was estimated by fusion of perceptions to the existence of damage from individual sensing paths. Assuming that there are m sensing paths for damage identification from the sensor network, the probability of the presence of damage at position (x, y) in the monitoring area is [17],

$$P(x, y) = \sum_{k=1}^m P_k(x, y) = \sum_{k=1}^m DI_k f_k(z) \quad (4)$$

Where DI_k and $f_k(z)$ are the DI, defined in Equations (2) or (3), and the normal distribution function for the k -th path way, respectively.

This process was applied to each individual path, and $P(x, y)$ at each grid was obtained for the area. In this way, perceptions of the damage were fused for all the paths, in which the existence of damage was highlighted by an area with high values of $P(x, y)$.

For the existence of damage at a location near the wave path, the effect of DI is confined in a bell shape with a normal distribution function, which means that the effect of DI is maximized on the

wave path and decreases gradually as the distance from the wave path increases,

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(z-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \text{ For } -\infty < z < \infty \quad (5)$$

μ and σ were set to 0 and 40 mm respectively based on experimental investigations where the sensitivity of the guided wave to debonding in a sandwich structure with uniform thickness was determined [20]. Further, the perception to damage along a sensing path), modulated by the weighted function, Equation (4), can be further refined along the path. An approach was investigated to determine the value of z in an elliptical zone for each sensing path, $z = \frac{D_a + D_s}{D_k}$, where D_k is the distance between the actuator and sensor for the k -th sensing path, while D_a and D_s are the distances between a node to the actuator and the sensor, respectively [19]. During the fusing process, the perception to the damage in an elliptical zone is strengthened for the grids near the middle section of the path.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Residual Deformation Due To Indentation Damage

The quasi-static indentation process on the beam was conducted using a steel indenter of a semi-sphere head (of 20 mm in diameter) with the tip sitting at the edge of the beam (Fig. 2a). Using a controlled displacement mode on the MTS-810, the indentation depth was increased gradually from 1 mm to 8 mm in a step of 1 mm at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min. The position of the indentation was 250 mm to the left of PZT 1. After every indentation step, the dent depth on the beam surface (referred to as the residual deformation) is measured using a depth micrometer. Two composite sandwich beams were tested.

It was observed that the residual deformation increases with an increase in the quasi-static indentation depth in almost a linear manner, and the 6 mm indentation resulted in the residual deformation of almost 1 mm (normally referred to as the smallest level of BVID), shown in Fig 2b.

The quasi-static indentation led to crushing in the honeycomb core and delamination in the CF/EP composite skin. The microscopic examination showed delamination after 3 mm indentation, in Fig. 3a. After reaching an indentation depth of 7 mm, the

damage became more visible where fibre breakage occurred in the CF/EP composite laminate as Fig. 3b. The residual deformation was 1.4 mm after an indentation depth of 8 mm.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. Indentation on CF/EP sandwich beams: (a) indentation set-up and (b) indentation depth versus residual deformation

After each step of the indentation, PZT 1 was actuated at a range of central frequencies to excite the A_0 and S_0 Lamb wave modes. The propagating waves were then captured using PZT 2 and PZT 3. Hilbert transform was applied to get the peak magnitude of the captured wave signals. The DI was defined based on Equation (3), where the magnitude of the wave signal was recorded in the intact beam first, which was later used as the benchmark for the damaged ones.

Fig. 3. Damage in honeycomb core and CF/EP composite laminate after indentation of (a) 3 mm and (b) 7 mm

Firstly, the excitation frequencies of 10 and 20 kHz were used to generate the A_0 mode. It was noticed that the DI increased clearly with the residual deformation up to 1 mm, shown in Fig. 4 for the wave signals captured by both PZT 2 and PZT 3. This phenomenon could be attributed to local wave dispersion due to damage in the indentation area.

For the fundamental symmetric modes S_0 , a relatively high excitation frequency was used ranging from 75 to 250 kHz. Based on the wave signals captured by PZT 2 and PZT 3, the DI increased almost linearly with the residual deformation until it reaches 1 mm, when the DI sharply increases, shown in Fig. 5. The value of DI almost doubled after the indentation depth was increased from 6 mm to 7 mm; this could highlight the transition from BVID to the visible damage. The DI values at the central frequency larger than 200 kHz are significantly bigger than those at the lower excitation frequency.

Fig. 4. Effect of BVID on DI based on A_0 mode signals from (a) PZT 2 and (b) PZT 3

4.2 Detection Of BVID Based Lamb Waves In CF/EP Sandwich Panels

The indentation process was further applied to the CF/EP sandwich composite panels with the surface attached PZT sensor network until BVID was produced at 3 and 5 mm indentation (Fig. 6). The profile of BVID was measured using a dial indicator gauge, where a selected region of 50 mm by 50 mm in area around the indentation was meshed into square grids of 2 mm in size; the residual deformation depth was measured at every node when the specimen was mounted on an orthogonal X-Y table, showed as a 3D figure for both the 3 and 5 mm indentation in Fig. 7. The indentation of 3 mm resulted in the maximum residual depth of about 0.5 mm, which is barely visible, and however, when the indentation was increased to 5 mm, the damage reaches a dent depth of 2.7 mm.

The capability of guided waves in locating BVID in CF/EP sandwich panels was investigated. Based on the tuning of the frequency for wave signals from the previous studies [20], sinusoidal tonebursts of 7.5 cycles at a frequency of 200 kHz were selected to activate the S_0 mode. From the network of 16 PZT elements a total of 160 paths were available, but with the dual function of the PZT elements they could be reduced to 80 paths (e.g. instead of using both paths P1-P2 and P2-P1, only P1-P2 was employed). All the 80 paths were used to construct an image with the values of DI defined using the change in magnitude of transmitted wave signals, Fig. 8a. However, for the TR process some paths (with dashed lines in Fig. 8b) were very short and close to the corners (blind zone); therefore they were disregarded during the damage image construction.

Path P3-P8 and Path P2-P11 in the CF/EP sandwich panel were randomly selected in demonstrating the results; P3-P8 is away from the damage (less affected by the indentation damage) while P2-P11 passes through the indented area. The two reconstructed signals of the S_0 mode (after TR) are shown in Fig 9a, achieving a high similarity with DI of 0.05 (i.e. $\rho_{a,b} = 0.95$) for P3-P8 but a less similarity with DI of 0.13 for P2-P11. However, when the DI was defined based on the magnitude change (Fig. 9b), a DI of 0.0045 was obtained for P3-P8 while the DI for P2-P11 reached 0.28. Then, the value of DI for every path was obtained using Equations 2 and 3. Estimation of the presence of damage in every grid in the area covered by the sensing paths was obtained after the fusion of perceptions from individual paths (Equation 4).

Fig. 5. Effect of BVID on the S_0 mode, (a) response from PZT 2 (b) response from PZT 3

Fig. 6. CF/EP sandwich composite plate under quasi-static indentation

Fig. 7. Residual indentation profile of CF/EP sandwich plates: (a) 3 mm indentation and (b) 5 mm indentation.

Fig. 8. Sensor network paths: (a) Group I with 80 paths and (b) Group II with 64 paths

Fig. 9. DI after 5 mm indentation (at 200 kHz) based on (a) TR and (b) magnitude change

The BVID location after 3 mm indentation was estimated as in Fig. 10 using both the approaches to define the values of DI. The error in the prediction of the x-coordinate based on the TR algorithm was larger than that based on the magnitude change. In addition, the BVID location was also estimated when the indentation was increased to 5 mm (shown in Fig. 11); again the TR algorithm suffered lack of precision in locating the BVID resulting in an error in the x-direction, though it has an advantage without benchmarking to the wave signals at the stage without damage.

Fig. 10. Image of BVID after 3 mm indentation using DI based on guided wave signals, (a) magnitude change and (b) TR, with the “x” indicating the centre of the predicted location and “+” indicating the actual location

Fig. 11. Image of BVID after 3 mm indentation using DI based on guided wave signals, (a) magnitude change and (b) TR, with the “x” indicating the centre of the predicted location and “+” indicating the actual location.

5 Concluding Remarks

In this study, the interaction of guided ultrasonic waves, specifically the fundamental A_0 and S_0 Lamb wave modes, with BVID in CF/EP sandwich panels with honeycomb core was investigated.

It was observed that the residual deformation on the CF/EP laminate skin is almost linearly correlated with the indentation depth for the sandwich beams. The residual deformation in the beams is much smaller than that in the panels after the same indentation depth.

Both the A_0 and S_0 modes showed good sensitivity to a residual dent depth as small as 0.2 mm. The damage index, DI, based on the magnitude of transmitted wave signals benchmarking the undamaged one or the coefficient of correlation

between the transmitted and reconstructed wave signals were used to quantitatively define the severity of BVID. Using the DI from multiple sensing paths of the surface-attached PZT elements, the location of BVID in the CF/EP sandwich panels was successfully defined using an inverse algorithm, and the approach with DI based on the magnitude of transmitted wave signals showed more accurate results in the location of BVID

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